

Implications of Limited Perspective in Property Market Investment Decision-Making: A Study of Plateau State, Nigeria

by

Dashol Ishaya Usman

Plateau State University Bokokos,

Department of Economic

dashol@plasu.edu.ng

Abstract

The purpose of the study was to establish the implications of limited perspectives on investment decision-making in the property market in Plateau State, Nigeria. Descriptive research design was used in the study. The study population consisted of property agents who were investment traders at the property market in Plateau State and currently registered and licensed to operate in Plateau State property market in Nigeria. The target population comprised 1650 registered property investors trading at the property market in Plateau State and currently licensed to operate in Plateau state property market in Nigeria. Property investors were targeted. Multi-stage sampling procedure was used in the selection of representative sample consisting of purposive sampling and the normal approximation to the hyper-geometric distribution to select the sample size. The final sample size was thus composed of 312 respondents. Primary data was collected using standard questionnaires with both closed and open ended questions. The regression analysis results confirmed that there was a significant positive linear relationship between narrow framing and investor investment decision making in the property market in Plateau State in Nigeria. The study concluded that limited perspectives affected investment decisions. The main recommendation for investors is to make constant attempts to increase their awareness on behavioral finance by educating themselves on the field. Studying about the biases, and reflecting on their decisions are likely to help achieve better self-understanding of the extent and manner to which they get influenced by emotions while making financial decisions under uncertainty.

Keywords: Limited Perspective, investment decision-making, property market

Introduction

Background of the Study

Investment in property is viewed as an engine of sustainable growth (Ahn & Hemmings, 2000). However, in less developed countries (LDCs) the national level of savings is very low (Javorcik & Smarznska, 2004). Thus, there is a wide gap between the required rate of investment in the property market and the existing rate of such investments (Asiedu, 2006). The Brussels Declaration enclosed 30 worldwide development goals for LDCs, together with the realization of an investment to GDP ratio of 25 per cent and an annual GDP growth rate of at least 7 per cent in order to attain sustainable progress and poor quality reduction in LDCs (United Nations, 2010). Behavioural economists attribute the imperfections in property markets globally to certain biases. These biases include cognitive biases such as overconfidence, overreaction, representative bias, information bias, and various other predictable human errors in reasoning and information processing. These have been researched by psychologists such as Kahneman (1979), Tversky (1979), Thaler (1994), and Slovic (2000).

A cognitive bias is a systematic discrepancy between the “correct” answer in a judgmental task, given by a formal normative rule, and the decision makers and experts' actual answer to such a task (Kahneman, Slovic, Tversky, 1982; and Gilovich, Griffin, Kahneman, 2002). Thus, cognitive biases can further be viewed as a negative consequence of adopting heuristics. They are a discrepancy between someone’s judgment and reality and can be cognitive (Virine & Trumper, 2008). Decision makers also tend to make judgments based on an initial assessment as anchor, but fail to make sufficient adjustments later on. It is the tendency to rely on one trait or piece of information when making decisions. Virine and Trumper (2008) categorized several cognitive biases into four types: (i) behavioural biases and biases related to perception; (ii) biases in estimation of probability and belief; (iii) social and group biases; and (iv) memory biases and effects. Studies have also been conducted all over the world on the relationship between behavioural patterns of investors and investment decisions. Hussein and Al-Tamimi, (2006) investigated the factors influencing the United Arab Emirates (UAE) investor behaviour where it was found that six factors were the most influencing factors; expected corporate earnings, get rich quick, stock marketability, past performance of the firm's stock, government holdings, the creation of the organized financial market.

The Nigerian property market has evolved extensively with great opportunities for investors, particularly in states like Rivers, Kano, Enugu, Kaduna, Oyo, Lagos and the capital city Abuja have witnessed great upturn of investors, plunging millions of dollars in the real estate sector, especially in the commercial sectors. The growing interest in the Nigerian Market is due to high demand raised by the increase in urban population and change in shopping culture among the increasing population. These factors have resulted in the up spring of numerous shopping malls. The Nigerian property market remains attractive with numerous opportunities in the following sectors of the market; Retail Real Estate, Office blocks and Serviced Apartments (FHA, 2015).

Nigeria is made up of thirty states with Abuja as the capital city. Plateau State is situated in the North-Central and the middle belt zone of Nigeria. Jos is the capital city of Plateau State, linked by road, rail and air to other parts of the country. Plateau state is known among the thirty-six states in Nigeria to be endowed with cool and temperate climate as against other states in the country with hot weather conditions. This has attracted both serving and retired top government officials and businessmen from all parts of the country to invest in the property market in the state as most of them prefer to reside in the state after their retirement. The state has often been classified as a miniature Nigeria with virtually all the tribes in the country residing there. Apart from its favourable climate and tourist attractions, the state is also known to be blessed with natural resources such as tin, columbite, and lead among others. These resources have attracted investors from within and beyond which has resulted in the increase in property development by investors (Nwude, 2012). However, most of the investors tend to exhibit certain biases such as overconfidence, representativeness bias and herding in making their investment decisions in the property sector in Nigeria (Obamuyi, 2013).

Literature Review

Theoretical Background

Heuristic Theory

The proponents of heuristic theory were Amos Tversky and Daniel Kahneman in 1970's who revolutionized the academic research on human judgment/decision making. The central idea of the "heuristics and biases" was that judgment under uncertainty often rests on a limited

number of simplifying heuristics rather than extensive algorithmic processing. The popularity of this central idea soon spread beyond academic psychology, affecting theory and research across a range of disciplines including economics, law, medicine, business and political science. The message was revolutionary in that it simultaneously questioned the descriptive adequacy of ideal models of judgment and offered a cognitive alternative that explained human error without invoking motivated irrationality (Gilovich & Griffin, 2002).

Prospect Theory

Prospect theory was created in 1979 and developed in 1992 by Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky as a psychologically more accurate description of decision making. The theory states that people make decisions based on the potential value of losses and gains rather than the final outcome. In addition people evaluate these losses and gains rather than the final outcome and that people evaluate these losses and gains using certain heuristics (Tversky & Kahneman, 1979). Prospect theory is a theory of decision making under conditions of risk. Decisions are based on risks. Judgements are assessments about the external state of the world. They are made especially challenging under conditions of uncertainty, where it is difficult to oversee the consequences or outcome of events with clarity. Decisions involve internal conflict over value-trade-offs. They are made difficult when choices promote contradictory values and goals. The theory directly addresses how these choices are framed and evaluated in the decision making process, (Tversky & Kahneman 1979).

Theory of Planned Behaviour

The theory of planned behaviour (TPB) was introduced by Icek Ajzen in 2002 as a link between beliefs and behaviour. It was intended by Ajzen as an improvement on the earlier predictive power of the theory of reasoned action in 1980. The theory of reasoned action considers behavioural intention as the immediate motivator for individuals to perform the behaviour. Behavioural intention, in turn, is a function of two determining factors, namely attitude toward the behaviour (AT) and subjective norm (SN) that relate to conducting the behaviour (Ajzen & Fishbein 1980).

Attitude toward the behaviour is defined as one's general feelings indicating their favourableness or unfavourableness to the behaviour. Subjective norm is defined as one's perception regarding whether significantly others think the behaviour should be performed or not (Ajzen & Fishbein 1980). Despite the fact that TRA is widely accepted in literature, this

theory still contains limitations. It does not anticipate accurately behaviours constrained by a lack of opportunities or resources such as skills, time or capital to make investment decisions. This is even when individuals would otherwise be favourable of and socially urged to perform the behaviour (Ajzen 1991).

Empirical Literature Review

Limited Perspectives or Narrow framing according to Bailey, Nicholas, Andrei, Shleifer and Robert (2009) is the propensity of an investor to select investments individually, instead of considering the broad impact on the portfolio. Kahneman (2003) studied on prospect theory: an analysis of decision-making under risk. The findings were that limited perspectives (narrow framing) occurs when decisions are made intuitively rather than through systematic reasoning. Kahneman (2003) found that in a positive frame, the compromise between arriving at a good decision and minimizing cognitive effort is easy to achieve; for example, selecting the option in which “200 people will be saved” feels “correct” in an emotional sense and is effortless (i.e., no calculations are necessary).

Laing (2010) findings confirmed the existence of the limited perspectives and a sunk cost effect. In particular the lowering of the amount of sunk cost produced a higher mean funding outcome than that attained in the positive frame. With regards to cognitive factors a significant correlation between perception of responsibility and the amount of funding granted was identified. Rabin and Weizsacker (2008) results showed both in an experimental setting and using a large representative survey, that a majority of people choose dominated strategies when prospects were presented in isolation. But this disappeared when the joint distribution of these prospects was shown, consistent with limited perspectives driving their decisions. Importantly, they also proved theoretically that even small degrees of limited perspectives can result in people making dominated choices, provided preferences departed.

Barberis and Huang (2007) studied on Prospect Theory and Asset Prices in a small lottery firm using a sample size of 603 respondents. The findings were that, since regret comes from comparing the consequences of a specific action with those of a verifiable alternative, it leads people to focus on the outcomes of the action itself and ignore their contribution to overall wealth. Wang (2005) in a study on the adaptive decision maker and using a sample size of 400 stock brokers found that individual investors take longer to make decisions when the options are framed as losses rather than gains. The costs and benefits involved in this kind of

choices are of two types; cognitive and affective, and that both play a role in the framing effect. They also found that, the cognitive effort involved in calculating an expected value is larger in risky than in certain choices and on the other hand, the affective cost is higher for losses than gains

Research Methodology

The method used for data collection was based on the exploratory nature of the research using descriptive survey design. This is a type of non-experimental research design for collecting and analyzing data in order to describe the problem in its current status. Descriptive survey design was used in preliminary and exploratory studies to allow researchers to gather information, summarize, present and interpret for the purpose of clarification (Orodho, 2004). The study population comprised property investors who are investment traders at the property market in Plateau State and currently registered and licensed to operate. The focus was on registered office and rental residential properties in a sample of the seventeen Local Government headquarters of Plateau state. The sampling frame was comprised of a list of 1650 property investors extracted from the official records of Ministry of Lands and Survey in Plateau State, Nigeria

Multi-stage sampling procedure was used in the selection of representative samples. Purposive sampling was used to select the capital city of the state and some selected towns among the seventeen Local Government headquarters. The final sample size thus comprised 312 respondents. Primary data was collected using a questionnaire where a standard questionnaire with both closed and open ended questions were administered to capture the important information about the population. The study employed both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques to allow presentation of data in a more meaningful way and thus simpler interpretation of data

Model - Implications of Limited Perspectives on Investors' Decision Making in Property Market in Plateau State, Nigeria

$$ID = \beta_0 + \beta_3(LP) + \varepsilon$$

Where:

ID = Represents the Investment Decision

β_0 = Model intercept

β_3 = Represents the beta coefficient for Narrow Framing Bias

LP= Limited Perspectives

ε = Error term of the model

Analysis, Findings and Discussions

A total number of 312 questionnaires were administered to the property investors who are investment traders at the property market in Plateau State, Nigeria and currently registered and licensed to operate out of which 276 questionnaires were duly returned. This constituted 88.5% response rate.

Respondents Background Information

Table 1: Respondents Background Information

Category		Percent
Gender	Male	62.1
	Female	37.9
Level of Education	Less than 1 year	2.5
	1 - 2 years	2.2
	2 - 3 years	12.7
	3 - 4 years	41.7
	4 - 5 years	40.9
Total		100

The results indicated that 62% of the respondents were male while 38% were female. This was an indication that majority of the property investors who are investment traders at the property market in Plateau State and currently registered and licensed to operate were male

The findings in table 1 indicated that the majority (41.7%) of the respondents had worked for between 3 and 4 years. Those who had worked for between 4 and 5 years were 40.9%. The respondents who had worked for less than 1 year were 2.5%. These findings implied that the majority of the respondents had worked long enough to provide the information sought by the study.

Descriptive Analysis for Narrow Framing Bias

This study also sought to explain the influence of narrow framing on investment decision making in the property market in Plateau State, Nigeria. The descriptive findings are presented in

Table 2.

Table 1: Limited Perspectives Bias

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always	Mean	Std Dev
Investors usually make positive decisions on property investment	3.6%	3.3%	6.9%	44.9%	41.3%	4.17	0.96
Investors usually make negative decisions on property investment	4.3%	3.6%	6.5%	43.5%	42.0%	4.15	1.00
Mostly, investors usually combine positive and negative decisions on property investment	2.5%	6.5%	9.1%	38.0%	43.8%	4.14	1.00
Property investors evaluate risks while buying property	3.6%	3.6%	6.5%	44.6%	41.7%	4.17	0.96
Property investors evaluate risks while selling property	5.8%	4.3%	8.3%	39.5%	42.0%	4.08	1.09
Investors always evaluate risks in isolation, separately from other risks they are already facing	2.2%	4.3%	8.3%	43.5%	41.7%	4.18	0.92
Investors derive utility from gains and losses in the value of individual properties	4.0%	4.0%	7.2%	42.0%	42.8%	4.16	1.00

The study sought to find out whether property investors usually make positive decisions on property investment, the findings revealed that the statement had a mean of 4.17 and standard deviation of 0.96 which showed that majority of the respondents agreed with the statement. The study was further interested in whether investors usually make negative decisions on property investment; similarly the statement had a mean of 4.15 showing agreement with the statement. On whether investors usually combined positive and negative decisions on property investment, the study established that the majority of the respondents indicated

always and often. The study further found that the majority of the respondents indicated that property investors in Plateau State, Nigeria often and always evaluated risks while buying and selling property, evaluated risks in isolation, separately from other risks they are already facing and finally Investors derived utility from gains and losses in the value of individual properties. The findings also implied that property investors in Plateau State, Nigeria had narrow framing during investment decision making.

The study further sought to find out the causes of narrow framing among property investors. All the statements in this section had a mean of above 4 which implied that the respondents indicated that property investors in Plateau State, Nigeria often and always made positive decisions on choice of property, avoided risky decision making in property investment, Some investors were more risk-averse than others and investors base their investment decisions on the selective decisions of buying or selling property. Similarly, the respondents agreed that fear of loss and level of tolerance were elements that impacted the narrow framing of individual investors, that property investors had tendency to follow the less risky alternative in making investment decisions and finally that confident property investors rely on calculated risks for the investment decisions.

Similarly, Kahneman (2003) found that in a positive frame, the compromise between arriving at a good decision and minimizing cognitive effort is easy to achieve. Laing (2010) used a sample size of 265 to test the existence of the framing effect and sunk cost effect whilst examining the influence of cognitive factors. The findings confirmed the existence of the limited perspectives and a sunk cost effect. Rabin and Weizsacker (2008) demonstrated that a majority of people choose dominated strategies when prospects were presented in isolation.

Correlation Results

The correlation analysis results revealed that limited perspectives and investors' investment decision making had a positive and significant association ($r=0.480$, $p=0.000$). Similarly, Kahneman (2003) found that in a positive frame, the compromise between arriving at a good decision and minimizing cognitive effort is easy to achieve. Laing (2010) used a sample size of 265 to test the existence of the limited perspectives and sunk cost effect whilst examining the influence of cognitive factors. The findings confirmed the existence of limited perspectives and a sunk cost effect. Rabin and Weizsacker (2008) demonstrated that a majority of people choose dominated strategies when prospects are presented in isolation.

Table 2: Correlation Results of Limited Perspectives and Investment Decision Making

		Investment Decision Making	Limited Perspectives
Investment Decision Making	Pearson Correlation	1	.480**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	276	276
Limited Perspectives	Pearson Correlation	.480**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	276	276

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Regression Analysis Results

The study further sought to find out the relationship between limited perspectives and investors' investment decision making. The study used a regression model to test the relationship between limited perspectives and investors' investment decision making among property investors in Plateau State in Nigeria. The study measured overconfidence bias using propensity to positive decision making, propensity to negative decision making and propensity to risk-taking in decisions.

Table 3: Model Summary for Limited Perspectives Bias and Investment Decision Making

Model	1
R	.748a
R Square	0.56
Adjusted R Square	0.555
Std. Error of the Estimate	0.41267
F (Sig.)	115.460 (0.000)

The results indicated that the model had an R-square of 0.560 which implied that propensity to positive decision making, propensity to negative decision making and propensity to risk-taking in decision biases jointly explained 56.0% of the variation in investment decision making. The F-statistic obtained was 115.460 with a p-value of 0.000 which further confirmed that there was a significant relationship between propensity to positive decision making, propensity to negative decision making and propensity to risk-taking in decisions and investment decision making.

Table 4: Coefficient for Limited Perspectives Bias and Investment Decision Making

	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	1.599	0.138		11.576	0.000
Propensity to risk-taking in decisions	0.233	0.029	0.377	8.002	0.000

Propensity to negative decision making	0.203	0.028	0.328	7.205	0.000
Propensity to positive decision making	0.166	0.029	0.256	5.655	0.000

a Dependent Variable: Investment Decision

Propensity to positive decision making, propensity to negative decision making and propensity to risk-taking in decisions were all found to have a positive and significant relationship with investment decision since their respective p-values were less than 0.05. However, the influence of propensity to risk-taking in decisions was greater as shown by the $\beta = 0.233$, followed by propensity to negative decision making ($\beta=0.203$). Finally, propensity to positive decision making had the least effect on investment decision making.

Overall Regression Analysis for Limited Perspectives and Investors' Investment Decision Making

The overall model summary revealed that R squared was 0.230 which implied that 23.0% of the variation in investors' investment decision making could be explained by limited perspectives bias.

Table 5: Model Summary for Limited Perspectives and Investment Decision Making

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.480 ^a	.230	.228	.54386

a. Predictors: (Constant), Limited Perspectives Bias

F-test was further carried out to test the null hypothesis that there is no significant impact of limited perspectives bias and investors' investment decision making in the property market in Plateau State in Nigeria. The results of ANOVA test show that the F value is 82.042 with a significance of p-value = 0.000 which was less than 0.05, meaning that null hypothesis was rejected and conclude that there is a relationship between limited perspectives bias and investors' investment decision making in property market in Plateau State, Nigeria. The results also implied that limited perspectives was a significant predictor of investors' investment decision making.

Table 6: ANOVA Results for Limited Perspectives and Investment Decision Making

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	24.267	1	24.267	82.042	.000 ^b

Residual	81.046	274	.296
Total	105.313	275	

a. Dependent Variable: Investment Decision Making

The results on the beta coefficient of the resulting model showed that the constant $\alpha = 2.542$ was significantly different from 0, since the p-value = 0.000 was less than 0.05. The coefficient $\beta = 0.391$ was also significantly different from 0 with a p-value = 0.000 which was less than 0.05. The results imply that a unit change in limited perspectives bias would result in 0.391 units change in investment decision making in the property market in Plateau State, Nigeria. This further confirmed that there was a significant positive linear relationship between Limited Perspectives and investors' investment decision making in the property market in Plateau State in Nigeria.

Table 7: Coefficient for Limited Perspectives and Investment Decision Making

	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	2.542	0.175		14.551	0.000
Limited Perspectives	0.391	0.043	0.48	9.058	0.000

a Dependent Variable: Investment Decision Making

Similarly, Kahneman (2003) found that in a positive frame, the compromise between arriving at a good decision and minimizing cognitive effort is easy to achieve. Laing (2010) used a sample size of 265 to test the existence of the framing effect and sunk cost effect whilst examining the influence of cognitive factors. The findings confirmed the existence of limited perspectives and a sunk cost effect. Rabin and Weizsacker (2008) demonstrated that a majority of people choose dominated strategies when prospects were presented in isolation.

Conclusion

The study further established that limited perspectives or narrow framing bias had a significant influence on investment decision making. The study concluded that due to the influence of limited perspectives, investors may make different choices according to the same information but under different statement frames. Therefore, investors must be careful when making investment decisions since they are likely to be influenced by limited perspectives bias.

Recommendations

Due to the influence of limited perspectives, investors may make different choices according to the same information but under different statement frames. The study therefore recommends the need for investors to make constant attempts to increase their awareness on behavioral biases by educating themselves on the field. Studying about the biases and reflecting on their decisions are likely to help achieve better self-understanding of the extent and the manner to which they get influenced by emotions while making financial decisions under uncertainty. Even after satisfactory awareness is achieved, it is highly recommended that they maintain a chart of the behavioral biases they are likely to be vulnerable to. This should be reviewed periodically in order to recollect and refresh their memories, thus giving themselves a better chance to make improved financial decisions in the property market. Most essentially, what remains unanswered is whether greater awareness of investors about behavioral biases is likely to increase the market efficiency.

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